

1 Innate immune activation by checkpoint inhibition in patient-derived lung cancer tissues
2 Supplementary Information

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Fig. S1. Primary NSCLC tissue of UK131 patient stains positive for squamous cell carcinoma marker, PD-1 and PD-L1. Freshly resected CA lung tissue of UK131 was FFPE-processed, sectioned as 4 μ m slices, stained for KRT5 (squamous cell carcinoma marker)/HIF1 α in **A**, PD-1/CD8 in **B**, and PD-L1/CD206 in **C**, and analyzed by confocal microscopy as described in the Materials and Methods.

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Fig. S2. Brain-metastasized NSCLC tissue of UK2035 patient stains positive for neuroendocrine markers, PD-1 and PD-L1. Freshly resected CA lung tissue of UK2035 was FFPE-processed, sectioned as 4 µm slices, stained for CgA/NCAM1 (neuroendocrine tumor markers) in **A** and PD-1/PD-L1/CD8 in **B**, and analyzed by confocal microscopy, as described in the Materials and Methods.

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Fig. S3. M1 polarization of human M ϕ activates the PPP and glycogen synthesis. Two-day polarized M1- M ϕ (■) and M2-M ϕ (■) plus naïve M ϕ (M0, ■) prepared from a 65-year old male donor were treated with $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -Glc for 24 h before extraction for polar metabolites and analysis by IC-UHR-FTMS (a-h) and 1D HSQC NMR (i), as described in the Materials and Methods. All symbols and abbreviations are as in Fig. 1. Data are displayed as mean \pm sem. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.005$.

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Fig. S5. M1 polarization of human M ϕ enhances the release of proinflammatory effectors. M0-, M1-, and M2-M ϕ were derived from PBMC of the same donor as in Fig. S3. Media from M0- (■), M1- (■), and M2-M ϕ (■) (n=2) were analyzed for cytokines and chemokines as described in Materials and Methods. Data are displayed as mean \pm sem. * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.005

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Fig. S6. Pembro+WGP attenuates central energy and anabolic metabolism in OTCs of brain-metastasized NSCLC tissues from UK2035 patient. CA lung OTCs of UK2035 patient were treated with Ctl (■), 40 µg/mL Pembro (■), 0.1 mg/mL WGP (■) (n=3), or Pembro + WGP combined (P+W ■) (n=2) in the presence of $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{-Glc}$ for 24 h before extraction for polar metabolites and analysis by IC-UHR-FTMS, as described in the Materials and Methods. The diagrams in **A-D** depict atom-resolved transformation of $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{-Glc}$ via glycolysis+the Krebs cycle, the PPP+glycogen synthesis pathway, and pathways of pyrimidine and purine nucleotide synthesis, respectively. Base in X-axis of **C** and **D** denotes ^{13}C -labeled isotopologues of pyrimidine and purine bases. OMP: orotidine 5'-monophosphate; IMP: inosine 5'-monophosphate. All other symbols and abbreviations are as in **Figs. 1-2**. Data are displayed as mean±sem. * $p < 0.05$.

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Table S1

Patient #	UK131	UK2035
Tumor Type	Moderately differentiated squamous cell carcinoma	Metastatic large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma
TNM Staging (pT)	T1c	
TNM Staging (pN)	N0	
TNM Staging (pM)	–	
Tumor Grade	2	
Tumor PET SUV		
FEV1/FVC ratio	74	58
Gender	F	M
Age	54	55
Ethnicity	white	white
Comorbidity	COPD	COPD
smoking history (pack years)	35	–

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Table S2. Information on primary antibodies used for immunofluorescent staining.

Antibody	Clone	Species	Source	Product #	Dilution
PD-L1	E1L3N	Rabbit	Cell Signaling	13684	1:200
PD-1	EH33	Mouse	Cell Signaling	43248	1:200
Cytokeratin 5	1A1C5	Mouse	Proteintech	66727-1-Ig	1:10000
CD8 α	C8/144B	Mouse	Cell Signaling	70306	1:200
CD8 α (DSP)	OTI3H6	Mouse	Origene	CF802079	1:200
CD68 (DSP)	KP1	Mouse	SCBT	sc-20060	1:400
HIF1 α		Rabbit	Proteintech	20960-1-AP	1:50
CD206	D-1	Mouse	Santa Cruz	sc-376108	1:100
Chromogranin A	3H11C11	Mouse	Proteintech	60135-1-Ig	1:5000
NCAM1/CD56		Rabbit	Proteintech	14255-1-AP	1:2000
PCNA	PC10	Mouse	Cell Signaling	2586	1:4000
Pancytokeratin (DSP)	AE1/AE3	Mouse	Invitrogen	53-9003-82	1:500
RIP	D94C12	Rabbit	Cell Signaling	3493	1:100
Caspase 3		Rabbit	Proteintech	19677-1-AP	1:200

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